

RISK ASSESSMENT OF LEAD IN SOIL: AN ALTERNATIVE APPROACH TO CALCULATE MAXIMUM TOLERABLE LEVELS

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SUMMARY

Based on the Soil Protection Act, the necessity of remediation is determined on the basis of intervention values, which were arrived at by modelling the potential risk that contaminated soil poses for humans and the ecosystem. The remediation urgency is determined by means of a risk assessment that includes site-specific information. According to this methodology, the diffuse contamination of urban areas with lead may form an actual risk for young children. Critical examination however showed that this outcome is based on conservative model assumptions. Using an alternative approach based on a mass balance study of lead in children, it was calculated that actual risks are only expected to occur at levels that are higher than the Dutch intervention values.

KURZFASSUNG

Im niederländischen Bodenschutzgesetz wurde die Notwendigkeit einer Bodensanierung durch Interventionswerte festgelegt. Diese Werte werden anhand von möglichen Gefahr für Mensch und Umwelt bestimmt. Die Dringlichkeit wird mittels einer Schätzung der aktuellen Risiken auf der Grundlage der standortspezifischen Gegebenheiten ermittelt. Nach einer solchen Schätzung müßte für eine diffuse Kontamination von Blei in städtischen Gebieten ein aktuelles Risiko für Kinder bestehen. Bei einer Analyse dieser Risiken wird jedoch ersichtlich, daß dieses Ergebnis aufgrund konservativer Modellannahmen zustande kommt. Mit einer alternativen Schätzung, die auf einer Massenausgleichsstudie von Blei basiert, sind aktuelle Risiken für Kleinkinder erst bei Konzentrationen zu erwarten, die höher als die heutigen Interventionswerte liegen.

RÉSUMÉ

La Loi sur la Protection des Sols aux Pays-Bas formule l'obligation de la nécessité de la dépollution en contaminant dépassant les seuils d'intervention. Ces seuils ont été déterminés en fonction des risques potentiels pour la santé publique ou pour l'environnement. L'urgence de la réalisation d'une telle dépollution doit être évaluée par une estimation des risques actuels, sur la base de circonstances spécifique au site. Lors d'une telle évaluation, il est apparu que des risques actuels pour la santé des enfants peuvent se produire en présence d'une pollution diffuse par le plomb, dans les sols de grandes agglomérations. Un examen critique montre en revanche que l'existence présumée de risque est surtout le résultat de suppositions conservatrices. Une approche alternative, par le biais de l'étude du bilan massique du plomb montre par contre que des risques n'existent qu'à des teneurs en plomb bien supérieures aux seuils d'intervention.

INTRODUCTION

In 1994 the Dutch Ministry of Housing, Planning and Environment presented a new system for assessing soil contamination (VROM, 1994). It uses intervention values, describing potential risk of contaminated soil or ground water for public health or the ecosystem. Exceeding the value does imply soil remediation. As intervention values are derived from potential risk, the urgency for measures to be taken is to be defined by an assessment of actual risks. The actual risk for man can be judged using an exposure model that is taken site specific information into account. When the total exposure to a contaminant at a site is exceeding the Tolerable Daily Intake (TDI) of the chemical involved, then one is dealing with an actual risk. It can be concluded that need and urgency for remediation of a contaminated site, becoming from human risk, will depend on the exposure at the site and the TDI of the chemical. Besides, as exposure models are used to define the amount of exposure, numerical values for model parameters will determine the results of the risk assessment. And vice versa, by setting the relevant parameters one can adjust the assessment.

Dealing with lead, the following remarks are of interest. A TDI of $3.6 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ body weight.day was set for calculation of intervention values (Vermeire *et al.*, 1991). It was stated that the TDI was based on the most critical toxic effect, being neurological development by younger children. The model CSOIL (Van den Berg, 1991) that was used to calculate site specific exposure does assume a daily intake of soil particles of 150 mg, similar to 10 mg soil/kg body weight.day for younger children. Now it can be calculated that 360 mg lead per kg soil will fulfil the TDI for the younger children, if exposure is supposed to come from soil ingestion. If one includes an additional exposure from contaminated vegetables, the permissible levels can even go down to 120 mg lead/kg soil.

In the Netherlands a diffuse contamination of lead in soil can be found in urban areas, from various sources, exceeding the critical level of 360 mg/kg. When found in domestic gardens, a remediation is urgently needed, according to the Dutch methodology as described earlier. Thus, the consequence of the risk assessment of contaminated soil is a demand for remediation of sites contaminated by lead from diffuse sources, such as former used leaded gasoline. One can argue whether or not this outcome is demonstrating a realistic problem, or that the problem is just made by the method of risk assessment of contaminated soil due to the model estimations. Therefore, the various model assumptions needs for a closer look, and eventually an alternative approach for calculation critical levels of lead in soil has to taken into consideration.

MODEL ASSUMPTIONS

As stated, the problem of a widespread diffuse contamination of soil with lead is due to the model calculus, predicting an exceeding of the (Dutch) TDI for younger children from soil ingestion. One has to focus on the daily intake of soil, the

algorithm that computes exposure, and the relation between exposure and TDI.

Soil Ingestion

The amount of soil, ingested by younger children is subject to a lifelong discussion. Kimbrough *et al.* (1984) used for a risk assessment of dioxin a figure of 1000 mg soil/day. Calabrese *et al.* (1989) reported a daily ingestion in a range of 3 to 279 mg, and the USEPA (1989) uses 100 mg/day as an overall estimate for children 1 to 7 years of age. Van Wijnen (1990) reported a study by children aged 1 to 5 years, living in inner cities, with and without domestic gardens, and children staying on a camping with maximal possibilities for soil contact. His results showed no significant differences for children in the city with or without a domestic garden. The amount ingested was in the order of 0 to 90 mg soil/day. At a camping, daily ingestion was from 150 up to above 300 mg soil. As described earlier, ingestion is 150 mg/day according to the CSOIL model.

Intake and uptake

The exposure model calculates exposure from soil ingestion by multiplying the amount of soil ingested and the concentration in soil of the chemical involved. It can therefore be noticed, that the model estimates an external dose: intake. For lead are the low dose adverse effects caused by the mobile fraction of absorbed lead within the body. The amount actually detectable within the body (for example in blood) is defined by the internal dose after gastrointestinal absorption: uptake. However, CSOIL uses a figure of 100% for the gastrointestinal absorption for lead, suggesting uptake similar to intake.

TDI

For most chemicals the TDI is derived from laboratory studies with experimental animals, such as mice or rats. By controlling exposure at different doses, one can characterize a dose response relationship. From the dose response curve one does define a dose without effect: the No Effect Level (NEL) for the experimental animal. A TDI for humans is set from the NEL by means of a safety factor approach. Therefore, the TDI is an estimation of a no effect level for humans. In practice, studies with experimental animals are carried out by mixing pure chemicals with animal feed, or dissolving these in drinking water. In such cases the TDI is derived from an external dose, and one does not have to bother about the gastrointestinal absorption. However, it is known for many chemicals, that bioavailability of the chemicals may differ for the various matrices, as animal feed or soil. Some chemicals may be bound to soil particles, and its bioavailability will be lower from soil than from animal feed. For lead, animal studies with lead acetate in animal diet or in urban soil showed a retention from soil three times lower than from feed, on average (Chaney *et al.* 1984). Consequently, when using a TDI that was derived

from an external dose in animal feed, the risk will be overestimated by CSOIL three times for an assessment of a soil contamination.

There exists a lot of information on toxic effects of lead by humans from epidemiological studies. In these studies, levels of lead in blood are most often used as a marker for exposure. According to the USEPA (1989) are critical findings likely to occur by children above 150 μg lead/L blood. From a risk assessors point of view are the latter figures for lead in blood better suited to evaluate exposure of humans than the TDI. In practice however, monitoring of lead blood levels is only a useful tool after actual exposure. Setting preventive standards such as intervention values for tolerable levels of lead in soil, from maximal levels in blood needs far more effort. That effort is worthwhile as it is grounded on more reliable human toxicological data, and therefore needs less safety and uncertainty factors. It can be done by use of a pharmacokinetic model of lead, that calculates concentrations in relevant human tissues, after exposure of lead from different sources.

THE PHARMACOKINETIC MODEL

The pharmacokinetic model for lead is a two compartment, first order kinetic model. That means, that the human body can be divided into two major compartments, and that the lead is eliminated from the body by excretion of the first order. Such a model will show, that after a single dose the chemical will be rapidly distributed over the compartments after uptake, and will be eliminated from the body over time, proportional with its body burden. The time needed for elimination depends on the chemical, and is most often expressed as an elimination half-life. After repetitive dosing the percentage excreted per period of time will increase, and at a certain period the uptake and excretion are in equilibrium: in steady state. The moment can be described by the mathematical relationship:

$$\text{uptake} \times \text{elimination half-life} = \text{body burden} \times \ln(2).$$

The uptake is identical to the intake times the gastrointestinal absorption. Besides, it can be said, that steady state takes place after about four to five times the half-life. On the other hand, if not yet in steady state, the ratio between uptake and excretion can be considered a constant.

For lead there are two compartments. One: the blood and soft tissues such as kidneys and brain, and two: the bones. Half life for blood and soft tissue in humans is a month, whereas half life for the skeleton is said to be in the order of 10 to 30 years. That means, that both for children and adults lead in blood and soft tissue is in steady state. Lead in bones is increasing at a constant rate for children and young adults, and only for the elderly in steady state. Therefore, lead will be distributed after gastrointestinal absorption, and then eliminated from blood and soft tissue. Excretion is done in the urine for 75% or more, and in lesser extent in hair and nails, and by sweating (8%), according to Krasowski and Doelman (1990). Rest will accumulate in the bones. Due to the long elimination half-life in bones, one can be

assume that for young children elimination from the bones will not occur. It can then be calculated, that although a few percent of the original external dose will be stored in the bones, finally 95 to 99% of the body burden of lead is present in the skeleton of elderly.

A MASS BALANCE OF LEAD BY CHILDREN

The pharmacokinetic model was used to estimate the relationship between daily exposure to lead, and the levels of lead in blood for a young child. It was shown by Slob *et al.* (1993) and Van Diek (1994), that the levels of lead in blood are rather similar for children of one to six years of age. It was decided to focus on children of two to three years of age, being those ingesting the largest amount of soil, according to Van Wijnen (1990). Purpose was to set the mass balance of lead in the children. Data representing body burden, and exposure were selected from available data for 1980 and 1992, as shown in table 1. The reason for testing two different periods was to get a better estimate for the rate of gastrointestinal absorption in the model, that is not well known for humans.

Table 1. Concentrations of lead in blood, food and air, as reported for 1980 and 1992

	1980	1992
lead in blood [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	150 ¹	40 ²
food [$\mu\text{g/day}$]	80 ³	20-30 ⁴
air [$\mu\text{g/m}^3$]	0,4 ¹	0,08 ¹

¹ Slob *et al.*, 1993

² Van Diek, 1994

³ Krasowski and Doelman, 1990

⁴ estimated from data for 1985 by Krasowski and Doelman, 1990

From the data the body burden of a child of two to three years was estimated. The blood volume in infants is about 12% of the body weight, being 2 L on average (USEPA, 1989). Therefore, the body burden in steady state is 2 times the concentration in blood, plus half of it in the soft tissues, being 450 μg lead for a child in 1980 and 120 μg lead in 1992. According to the kinetics using a half life of 30 days, daily uptake had to be 11 μg ($450 \mu\text{g} \times \ln(2)/30$) in 1980, and 3 μg ($120 \mu\text{g} \times \ln(2)/30$) in 1992.

Intake

To estimate intake for a young child one has to consider intake from food, air, soil, and water. Results are summarized in table 2.

Food Intake data on food is available for adults only. The energy need of the young child is about 50% of those for adults (Geigy Scientific Tables, p.233). Assuming a diet, equally contaminated with lead both for adults and children, intake by a young child is half of the data given for adults, leading to an exposure of 40 μg lead/day in 1980, and 10 to 15 μg /day for 1992 from food on average.

Air Using a ventilation rate of 5 m^3/day (USEPA, 1989), intake can be calculated 2 and 0.4 μg lead/day from inhalation of air, on average.

Soil Intake from soil is to be expected, according to the ingestion data of Van Wijnen (1990). As described before, the estimate of the daily ingestion of 150 mg soil is rather conservative, and applying to situations with a maximal possibility for soil contact. A more representative figure should be in the order of 50 mg soil/day. As an average concentration of lead in soil, one could use the "reference" value, describing average concentration for lead in not contaminated Dutch soil. A figure of 50 mg lead/kg soil was chosen. Contradictory to food and air, the average concentration in soil is not supposed to change substantially over the years. Then intake from soil by young children is about 2.5 to 7.5 μg lead/day.

Water Exposure from drinking water can be substantial, when drinking water is tapped from leaden conduit pipes. According to Krasowski and Doelman (1990) only 2 to 3% of Dutch households were exposed to lead in drinking water in 1981. It can be presumed that exposure from drinking water is decreased ever since. Therefore, the contribution of lead from drinking water to the average daily exposure is ignored.

Table 2. Estimation of average uptake and intake of lead by a young child from various sources, for 1980 and 1992, in μg lead/day

	1980	1992
uptake	11	3
intake		
food	40	10-15
air	2	0.4
soil	2.5-7.5	2.5-7.5

By comparison of uptake, as calculated from the body burden, and intake, one can

estimate the gastrointestinal absorption of the various exposure routes. As the major part of inhalation from air is from aerosol with a very small particle size, the particles will reach the deep end of the lungs. Only a small part is then exhaled, and the remaining will be absorbed by the lung. Accordingly, the rate of absorption can be expected to be very high: in the order of 75 to 100%. With an absorption after inhalation of 100%, the uptake from food and soil must be 9 and 2.6 μg lead/day. Assuming that gastrointestinal absorption from soil is one third of absorption from food as shown for the experimental animals, it can be calculated that gastrointestinal absorption from food is about 20% and from soil 7%.

MAXIMAL TOLERABLE LEVELS OF LEAD IN SOIL

After creating a mass balance for exposure and body burden of lead for young children, one can determine maximal tolerable levels of lead in soil. Starting point is the maximal tolerable level of lead in blood for younger children of 150 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ as mentioned previously. In steady state conditions, this is equal to an uptake of 11 μg lead/day. Using the exposure data of 1992, the daily uptake from food is 20% of 12.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{day}$, and 0.4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{day}$ from air, leaving an uptake of maximal 8 μg lead/day from soil. By a gastrointestinal absorption of 7%, maximal tolerable intake is 115 $\mu\text{g}/\text{day}$. Using a daily ingestion of 50 to 150 mg soil, the maximal level should be between 780 and 2300 mg lead/kg soil.

DISCUSSION

Kinetic approach

The kinetic approach to calculate critical levels of lead in soil overcomes a few shortcomings of the methodology used to calculate intervention values. It includes background exposure from other sources, uses data on potential differences in gastrointestinal absorption for various matrices, and is focused on human toxicological data. Outcome of the model prediction will be less conservative and more trustworthy, as it does not need for uncertainty and safety factors, or conservative estimations. However, the kinetic approach does ask for a lot of human data, or data from experimental animals. Yet, when dealing with chemicals causing problems on soil contamination from diffuse sources giving debatable need for remediation, an alternative approach can be worthwhile.

Maximal tolerable levels in soil

The tolerable levels of lead in soil are a few times higher than allowable from the conventional Dutch methodology of risk assessment of contaminated soil based on intervention values. Using the values proposed in this study, most of the concentrations of lead in urban soil do not need for an urgent remediation, whereas according to the Dutch method actual risks for humans exist on a series of sites with

large scale diffuse contamination. The result of the kinetic approach is supported by available data on lead in blood by children, living at contaminated sites exceeding the intervention values. Jans *et al.* (1989) did not find elevated levels of lead in blood by children from 3 to 13 years of age, living at a site with a diffuse contamination of lead from 1000 up to 3000 mg/kg dw. More recent, for children up to 6 years of age no correlations were found between lead in blood, and lead in soil of their gardens with concentrations in soil up to 1600 mg/kg dw. (Van Diek, 1994). It may be concluded, that the result of this study is taken into consideration at the regulatory framework that is dealing with diffuse contamination of soil with lead.

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REFERENCES

- Calabrese, E.J., Barnes, R.M., Stanek, E.J., Pastides, H., Gilbert, C.E., Veneman, P., Wang, X., Lasztity, A., and Kostecki, P.T. (1989) How much soil do young children ingest: an epidemiologic study. *Reg. Tox. Pharm.* **10**, 123-137
- Chaney, R.L., Sterrett, S.B., and Mielke, H.W. (1984) The potential for heavy metal exposure from urban gardens and soil. Cited in: Lead in soil: issues and guidelines. B.E.Davies and B.G.Wixson eds. *Environ.Geochem.Health* **11**, 105-129 (1989)
- Geigy Scientific Tables, Volume 1, 8 ed. C.Leitner ed. Ciba Geigy
- Jans, H.W.A., Meulenbelt, J., De Groot, G., and Savelkoul, T.J.F. (1989) Onderzoek naar de loodconcentratie in bloed bij kinderen van 3 tot en met 13 jaar, wonend in een met lood verontreinigd gebied te Borselle, uitgevoerd op 26 april 1989, RIVM, Bilthoven, rep.id. 348201.007
- Kimbrough, R.D., Falk, H., Stehr, P., and Fries, G. (1984) Health implications of 2378-TCDD contamination of residential soil. *J.Toxicol.Environ.Health* **14**, 47-93
- Krasowski, M., and Doelman, P. (1990) Lood in milieu en voeding in Nederland. CCRX, Bilthoven
- Slob, R., Van Wijnen, J.H., Jongemans-Liedekerken, G., Van der Weerd, R., Woudenberg, F., Vaessen, H.A.M., and Jongeneelen, F.J. (1993) De belasting met lood en PAK van jonge kinderen in verschillende omgevingsituaties. GG&GD, Amsterdam
- USEPA (1989) Review of the national ambient air quality standards for lead: exposure analysis methodology and validation. QAPS staff report, US Environmental Protection Agency, Research Triangle Park NC 27711
- Van Diek (1994) Lood, bodem en gezondheid. Dienst WVG/GGD Arnhem, in press
- Van Wijnen, J.H. (1990) Health risk assessment of soil contamination. *Thesis* Univ.Amsterdam
- Van den Berg, R. (1991) Blootstelling van de mens aan bodemverontreiniging. Een kwalitatieve en kwantitatieve analyse, leidend tot voorstellen voor humaan toxicologische C toetsingswaarden. RIVM, Bilthoven, rep.id. 725201.006
- Vermeire, T.G., Van Apeldoorn, M.E., De Fouw, J.C., and Janssen, P.J.C. (1991) Voorstel voor de humaan toxicologische onderbouwing van C-toetsingswaarden. RIVM, Bilthoven, rep.id. 725201.005
- VROM, (1994) Circulaire inwerkingstreding saneringsregeling wet bodembescherming, tweede fase, VROM/HME/Dir.Bodem, Den Haag, december 1994